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Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy for Optical Identification of Dental Materials Toward Minimally Invasive Treatment

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ABSTRACT Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) is a broadband optical technique (400–1600 nm) with demonstrated potential for caries detection. However, its capability to identify residual restorative materials—an unresolved clinical challenge—has not yet been systematically investigated. Current visual–tactile examination achieves only about 60% sensitivity, and no existing method provides reliable real-time guidance. This *in vitro* study is the first to evaluate DRS as a tool for the automated discrimination of dental restorative materials from sound tooth structure. Fifty extracted human premolars and molars, together with standardized specimens of four materials (composite resin, universal composite, resin-modified glass ionomer cement, and self-adhesive resin cement), were measured using a prototype fiber-optic DRS probe. In total, 1,080 spectral records were collected across six classes (four materials, dentin, and enamel). A two-layer neural network classifier achieved an accuracy of 98.1% (cross-validation error: 0.046), outperforming support vector machine (87.0%), Bayesian (88.0%), and k-nearest neighbour (90.7%) models. The results demonstrate that each material produces a distinct spectral fingerprint that is clearly separable from healthy dental hard tissues. In clinical practice, a DRS probe could provide objective, operator-independent, real-time feedback, enabling precise removal of existing restorations while preserving sound dentin, as well as targeted localization of obturation remnants during endodontic retreatment. Future work will focus on *in vivo* validation under intraoral conditions, probe miniaturization for endodontic applications, and the development of a comprehensive spectral reference database to support routine clinical use.

INDEX TERMS Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy, secondary caries, root canal retreatment, minimally invasive dentistry, optical diagnostics, dental restorative materials, fiber-optic probe, digital signal processing, machine learning, classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diagnosing dental caries and distinguishing healthy hard dental tissues from residual restorative materials remains a persistent challenge in clinical dentistry. The visual–tactile method is the most widely used diagnostic approach; however, a Cochrane meta-analysis [1] demonstrated its limited reliability, reporting a pooled sensitivity of 0.86 (95% CI: 0.80–0.90) and specificity of 0.77 (95% CI: 0.72–0.82), with wide prediction intervals for future studies. Considerable variability across individual studies (sensitivity: 0.16–1.00; specificity: 0–1.00) could not be explained by factors such as tooth surface type, prevalence of dentinal caries, or reference standard.

In the context of secondary caries adjacent to direct

restorations, the diagnostic challenge is even greater. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis [2], encompassing 25 studies, demonstrated that none of the evaluated detection methods—including visual and tactile examination, intraoral radiography, cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), quantitative light-induced fluorescence (QLF), laser fluorescence, and digital imaging fiber-optic transillumination (DIFOTI)—achieves satisfactory diagnostic accuracy. The pooled sensitivity of visual examination in laboratory settings was only 0.60, while intraoral radiography reached 0.59; specificity was somewhat higher (0.67 and 0.82, respectively) [1], [2].

A critical clinical problem arises during the removal of existing restorations, when the clinician cannot reliably dis-

tinguish residual restorative material from healthy tooth tissue. Modern composite resins are often optically indistinguishable from native tooth structure in the visible spectrum, increasing the risk of leaving residual material in the cavity [3] and thereby compromising treatment outcomes [4], [5]. A recent study [3] using hyperspectral imaging (400–1000 nm) and near-infrared spectroscopy (1550–1950 nm) demonstrated that composite and enamel cannot be reliably differentiated within the visible range: classification accuracy reached only 84% in the 400–1000 nm range, compared with 99.8% in the 1550–1950 nm range. Statistically significant differences were observed particularly in the 1750–1800 nm region [3].

In endodontic retreatment, preservation of radicular dentin is essential, as the loss of pericervical and radicular dentin significantly reduces the fracture resistance of treated teeth [6], [7]. Contemporary minimally invasive endodontic approaches emphasize the preservation of tooth structure, with precise and complete removal of existing root canal filling materials (gutta-percha and sealer) representing a critical step. However, the detection of residual obturation (root canal filling) remnants remains challenging: although a dental operating microscope may aid identification, stereomicroscopic analyses have shown that remnants frequently remain undetected [6], [8].

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) is an optical technique based on measuring the interaction of broadband light (typically 400–1600 nm) with different materials. It captures backscattered light from subsurface layers and analyzes its spectral characteristics. This principle enables the characterization of optical tissue properties—such as absorption and scattering coefficients and anisotropy—and allows discrimination between healthy enamel, dentin, and cementum and demineralized, caries-affected tissues. An *in vitro* study [9] on 100 extracted premolars and molars demonstrated that DRS achieves a sensitivity of 0.90–0.93 in caries detection, comparable to visual ICDAS scoring and DIAGNOdent, while providing superior specificity (0.98), overall accuracy (0.95), and a low false-positive rate (0.04). A doctoral thesis conducted at the First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University [10] reported a classification accuracy of 93.4% (sensitivity 95.8%, specificity 91.8%) with an AUC of 0.928 when validated against histology. More recently, the application of incremental deep learning to reflectance data achieved classification accuracies of 98.1% in the signal domain and 94.4% in the spectral domain [9], [11]–[13].

A key advantage of DRS lies in its broadband spectral range (400–1600 nm), which exceeds that of most conventional optical diagnostic methods. For example, laser fluorescence (DIAGNOdent) operates at a single wavelength (655 nm) and is susceptible to interference from saliva, plaque, and staining. In contrast, DRS exploits both visible and near-infrared regions, enabling deeper tissue penetration. The spectral region above 1400 nm is particularly important for differentiating composite materials from dental tissues due to differences in water absorption, as composites contain

FIGURE 1. The principle of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy data analysis presenting (a) a prototype device for data acquisition using a broadband light source, optical fibres, and two spectrometers and (b) a computational system for signal preprocessing, feature extraction, and machine learning classification with subsequent statistical validation.

significantly less water than enamel or dentin. Near-infrared imaging at wavelengths of 1460 nm and 1550 nm has been shown to provide substantially higher contrast between composite materials and dental tissues compared with imaging at 1300 nm [9], [14].

These findings support a scientifically grounded extension of DRS applications beyond caries detection toward the *in situ* identification and discrimination of dental materials. If DRS can reliably differentiate healthy from demineralized tissue, it is reasonable to expect that the distinct optical properties of composite resins, glass-ionomer cements, amalgam, gutta-percha, and endodontic sealers will yield unique reflectance spectra compared with healthy dentin. This capability could enable two key clinical applications: (1) precise removal of existing restorations without leaving residual material, and (2) targeted removal of root canal filling materials during retreatment while preserving radicular dentin.

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy has been widely reported [15]–[17] as a powerful tool for quantifying optical and physiological tissue properties across a range of biomedical applications, including intraoperative nerve identification [18] and detection of precancerous lesions in the oral cavity [19], [20]. In this technique, tissue is typically illuminated by a broadband light source delivered via optical fiber, and the reflected light—modified by scattering and absorption within the tissue—is collected by the same or a separate fiber (Fig. 1).

The aim of this study is threefold: (i) to measure and spectrally characterize diffuse reflectance signals from healthy permanent dental tissues (enamel and dentin) and from four representative restorative materials (composite resin, universal composite, resin-modified glass ionomer cement, and self-adhesive resin cement) across the 400–1600 nm range; (ii) to implement and compare four machine-learning classi-

fiers—support vector machine, Bayesian classifier, k-nearest neighbours, and a two-layer neural network—with respect to their ability to discriminate among six defined tissue and material classes; and (iii) to evaluate the translational potential of DRS-based optical identification as a real-time guidance tool for minimally invasive restorative procedures and pre-endodontic preparation, with the aim of avoiding both residual material retention and unnecessary removal of healthy radicular dentin.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the DRS data acquisition protocol, specimen preparation, signal processing, and machine-learning methodology, including feature extraction and classifier design. Section III presents the experimental results, including spectral reflectance profiles for all six classes and a comparative evaluation of classification performance. Section IV discusses the diagnostic implications of the proposed approach in relation to current clinical limitations and outlines the requirements for clinical translation. Finally, Section V summarizes the main conclusions and identifies directions for future research.

II. METHODS

A. DATA ACQUISITION

The principal investigator selected 50 sound permanent teeth (premolars and molars) without signs of caries or prior treatment. Regions of interest (ROIs) were defined on healthy enamel and dentin areas of each tooth based on macroscopic inspection and transillumination, without magnification.

A prototype device was used to measure tooth surface reflectance via a dual fiber-optic probe. One optical fiber delivered broadband light to the surface (Fig. 1), while the second fiber collected the reflected signal and directed it to two spectrometers. Measurements were performed in discrete intervals, with a real-time reflectance curve displayed to guide acquisition. The recorded data were exported in CSV format, with each measurement consisting of 10 repeated scans to ensure consistency.

To simulate common clinical scenarios, four types of dental materials were selected: composite resin (MatFillingE), universal composite (MatFillingG), resin-modified glass ionomer cement (MatFillingR), and self-adhesive resin cement (Sealant), as summarized in Table 1. MatFillingE and MatFillingG represent two compositionally distinct composite systems—a microfilled esthetic composite (Enamel Plus HRi BF2) and a universal nanohybrid composite (GC G-aenial A2)—included to assess whether DRS can discriminate not only between material classes but also between composite subtypes. Standardized test specimens were prepared as $0.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.5$ cm cubes according to the manufacturers' polymerization or setting protocols. Five measurement areas (ROIs), each with a diameter of 1 mm, were defined centrally on the upper surface of each specimen.

All ROIs (teeth and materials) were measured using a prototype fiber-optic diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) system developed in collaboration with an industrial research

laboratory. The system comprised a halogen broadband light source (400–1600 nm) and a handheld probe with two optical fibers separated by 0.85 mm. The fibers were connected to two spectrometers equipped with detectors covering complementary wavelength ranges, including the visible and near-infrared regions. Spectral calibration was performed against a Spectralon white reference standard prior to each measurement session. All measurements were conducted under standardized environmental conditions (temperature $23 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$; relative humidity $50 \pm 5\%$), with the probe positioned perpendicular to the ROI surface and without applied pressure. Each ROI was measured ten times, and the results were averaged to reduce random error.

Extracted human teeth, obtained for periodontal, orthodontic, prosthetic, or surgical indications, were included after each patient provided written informed consent for both extraction and research use. Following extraction, the teeth were debrided and stored at 4°C in 0.5% chloramine-T solution for one week for disinfection, and subsequently transferred to distilled water with weekly replacement. Prior to measurement, the teeth were cleaned using a rotary brush with abrasive paste (Depural Neo; SpofaDental; Jičín, Czech Republic) at 10,000 rpm and thoroughly rinsed with water.

The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee (protocol number 613/18 S-IV) and conducted in accordance with the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its subsequent amendments. Selected datasets are publicly available under “Dental Filling Materials” on IEEE DataPort (DOI: 10.21227/ddnc-5e65) and in the EU Zenodo repository (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.190382066) for further analysis [21].

TABLE 1. SPECIFICATION OF MATERIALS ANALYSED BY THE DIFFUSE REFLECTANCE SPECTROSCOPY.

Item	Notation	Material Specification
1	DentalSealant	Dental sealant: RelyX Unicem, 3M, St. Paul, MN, USA
2	MatFillingE	Composite resin: Enamel Plus HRi Bio Function BF2, Micrium S.p.A., Avegno, Italy
3	MatFillingG	Universal composite: GC G-aenial A2, GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan
4	MatFillingR	Resin-modified glass ionomer cement: RIVA LC A2, SDI, Bayswater, Australia
5	HealthyDentin	Tooth dentin
6	HealthyEnamel	Tooth enamel

Note: RelyX Unicem (3M) is clinically classified as a self-adhesive resin cement. The dataset notation “DentalSealant” is retained for consistency with the publicly available data repository [21].

B. DATA PROCESSING METHODOLOGY

Data processing methods in this domain combine signal processing techniques, numerical analysis, and computational intelligence within a general information technology framework [22], [23]. These approaches are broadly applicable across various fields, including dentistry [24], [25].

Algorithm 1 summarizes the fundamental steps of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) data evaluation for discriminating dental restorative materials from dentin and enamel.

Outlier removal was performed using median filtering of three consecutive values. Subsequent resampling ensured consistent reflectivity values across identical wavelength points, enabling the application of finite impulse response (FIR) digital filtering and reliable estimation of mean spectral characteristics.

The application of mathematical classification models enabled identification of the material used for dental restoration. Feature vectors associated with individual classes form the pattern matrix $\mathbf{P}_{R,Q}$, which is essential for model training and parameter optimization. Each pattern vector may include signal features derived from the time, frequency, or scale domains [26], depending on the selected transformation methods. Ideally, these features form compact and well-separated clusters in feature space, with minimal overlap between classes. The corresponding target vector $\mathbf{T}_{Q,1}$ assigns class labels to each pattern vector.

In this study, statistical features derived from the time domain were used to construct the pattern and target matrices $\mathbf{P}_{R,Q}$ and $\mathbf{T}_{Q,1}$, respectively. Classification was performed using Bayesian classifiers, support vector machines, and k-nearest neighbour methods. Their performance was compared with that of a two-layer neural network, whose outputs are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A1}_{S1,Q} &= f_1(\mathbf{W1}_{S1,R} \mathbf{P}_{R,Q}, \mathbf{b1}_{S1,1}) \\ \mathbf{A2}_{S2,Q} &= f_2(\mathbf{W2}_{S2,S1} \mathbf{A1}_{S1,Q}, \mathbf{b2}_{S2,1}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The network coefficients optimized during the learning process include the elements of the matrices $\mathbf{W1}_{S1,R}$, $\mathbf{W2}_{S2,S1}$ and bias vectors $\mathbf{b1}_{S1,1}$, $\mathbf{b2}_{S2,1}$. The first layer employs a sigmoidal activation function f_1 , while the second layer uses a probabilistic softmax function f_2 .

Classification performance was evaluated using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves [27], based on true

FIGURE 2. Reflectance spectra for (a) dental sealant, (b) MatFillingE, (c) MatFillingG, (d) MatFillingR, (e) healthy dentin, and (f) healthy enamel, as specified in Table 1, with all signals preprocessed using median filtering and a window of three consecutive reflectance values.

positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN). Overall accuracy was calculated as:

$$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

Model generalization performance was further assessed using leave-one-out cross-validation.

III. RESULTS

Figure 2 presents reflectance spectra obtained from a dataset comprising 1,080 measurements across six classes: dental sealant, MatFillingE, MatFillingG, MatFillingR, healthy dentin, and healthy enamel, as specified in Table 1. Each record was preprocessed using median filtering with a window of three consecutive values to reduce noise and eliminate outliers.

Algorithm 1 Methodology of the DRS signal processing

- 1) **Data acquisition:** Design of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy experiment across selected wavelength bands, including repeated measurements to reduce observational error.
- 2) **Signal processing:** Application of DSP methods including:
 - removal of outliers (gross errors),
 - interpolation to align data from different sensors,
 - data resampling using the least square method,
 - digital filtering for noise reduction.
- 3) **Data classification:** Implementation of computational intelligence and machine learning for:
 - feature extraction,
 - development and evaluation of classification models.
- 4) **Verification:** Validation of results and assessment of model performance.

FIGURE 3. Distribution of peak reflectance and corresponding wavelength for (a) dental sealant, (b) MatFillingE, (c) MatFillingG, (d) MatFillingR, (e) healthy dentin, and (f) healthy enamel, as specified in Table 1, with mean values for each class shown together with variability ranges expressed as c -multiples of the standard deviation ($c = 1, 1.5, 2$).

FIGURE 4. Classification of dental restorative materials and healthy tooth tissues into six categories presented in Table 1 using (a) support vector machine (SVM) and (b) neural network models, based on peak reflectance and corresponding wavelength features.

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF CLASSIFICATION METHODS FOR DISCRIMINATING SIX CLASSES—DENTAL SEALANT, MATFILLINGE, MATFILLINGG, MATFILLINGR, HEALTHY DENTIN, AND HEALTHY ENAMEL—AS DEFINED IN TABLE 1, INCLUDING CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY AND CROSS-VALIDATION (CV) ERROR METRICS.

Method	Accuracy [%]	CV Errors
Support vector machine	87.0	0.204
Bayesian method	88.0	0.157
5 nearest neighbours	90.7	0.074
Neural network	98.1	0.046

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of peak reflectance values and their corresponding wavelengths for all six classes. The figure includes mean values and variability ranges expressed as c -multiples of the standard deviation ($c = 1, 1.5, 2$). The dataset consists of 108 independent measurement locations, each recorded ten times to ensure repeatability and statistical robustness.

Figure 4 shows the classification results based on peak reflectance and corresponding wavelength features for the different dental materials and healthy tissues. Mean feature values for each of the six classes are displayed, together with decision boundaries obtained using the support vector machine (SVM) classifier and a two-layer neural network with sigmoidal and softmax activation functions. The resulting class boundaries illustrate the discriminative capability of the evaluated models.

Table 2 provides a comparative evaluation of four classification methods—support vector machine, Bayesian classifier, 5-nearest neighbour, and a two-layer neural network—for distinguishing among the six material and tissue classes defined in Table 1. The results are reported in terms of classification accuracy and cross-validation (CV) error for dental sealant, MatFillingE, MatFillingG, MatFillingR, dentin, and enamel.

IV. DISCUSSION

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) represents a promising modality for addressing diagnostic limitations in minimally invasive restorative dentistry and endodontics. In vitro studies have shown that DRS achieves higher specificity and overall accuracy in caries detection than visual-tactile

examination and laser fluorescence, with a low false-positive rate, supporting preservation of sound tooth structure [9], [12].

A major clinical challenge during removal of aged restorations is distinguishing residual material from healthy tissue. Composite restorations may become visually indistinguishable from enamel and dentin, while existing methods—including fluorescence-based devices and radiography—fail to reliably differentiate secondary caries from marginal defects or material degradation. By exploiting a broad spectral range (visible to near-infrared), DRS enables discrimination based on differences in absorption, scattering, and water content between dentin and restorative materials, providing real-time feedback during treatment [2], [4], [5], [14], [28].

In endodontics, DRS is particularly relevant at the pulp chamber floor, where residual restorative materials may obscure canal orifices. Their removal is essential but risks excessive loss of pericervical dentin if the material-tissue interface is unclear [6], [7]. Current approaches rely on magnification and operator experience; however, residual materials may still mimic dentin. A DRS probe could therefore act as a localized material-interface sensor, supporting minimally invasive endodontics by enabling accurate differentiation between restorative material and radicular dentin [6], [29].

The results confirm the strong discriminative capability of DRS. The two-layer neural network achieved 98.1% accuracy (CV error 0.046), outperforming SVM (87.0%, CV 0.204), Bayesian (88.0%, CV 0.157), and k -nearest neighbour (90.7%, CV 0.074) classifiers. This reflects the ability of neural networks to model non-linear relationships in spectral data. The lower performance of the linear SVM indicates that class separation is non-linear, while Bayesian and k -NN models only partially capture class structure. Notably, even the lowest-performing classifier exceeded the reported sensitivity of visual examination (0.60) and intraoral radiography (0.59) for secondary caries detection [2].

From a clinical perspective, a classification accuracy of 98.1% supports the use of DRS as an objective real-time material sensor. By comparing measured spectra with a reference database, the system could indicate whether the bur is contacting restorative material or sound tissue, reducing both residual material retention [2], [4] and unnecessary tissue removal [6], [30]. In pre-endodontic procedures, this approach enables targeted removal of restorative remnants while preserving critical pericervical dentin [6], [8], [31]. The investigated materials—composite resin, universal composite, resin-modified glass ionomer cement, and self-adhesive resin cement—represent common clinical scenarios in restorative dentistry, supporting the model's relevance [2], [4], [32].

Limitations include the in vitro design under controlled conditions; intraoral factors such as saliva, blood, biofilm, hydration variability, and probe angulation may affect spectral behavior. Standardized specimens do not fully reflect the complexity of aged restorations in situ, particularly in root canals or degraded margins [33]. Furthermore, only four

restorative material classes were included; endodontic materials will be addressed in future work, and broader spectral libraries will be required for clinical application.

Future work should focus on (i) *in vivo* validation, (ii) probe miniaturization and ergonomic optimization for endodontic access, (iii) development of comprehensive spectral databases, and (iv) implementation of real-time, user-friendly software supported by machine learning [9], [13], [20].

In summary, DRS is not intended to replace existing diagnostic methods but to complement them at a critical decision point—distinguishing between restorative material and sound tooth structure. With further validation, it may become an integral component of minimally invasive restorative and endodontic workflows.

V. CONCLUSION

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) is a promising optical modality with significant potential for minimally invasive restorative and endodontic procedures. *In vitro* studies have demonstrated that DRS achieves higher specificity and accuracy in caries detection than visual–tactile examination and laser fluorescence. Its broadband spectral range (400–1600 nm) enables discrimination not only between healthy and caries-affected tissues but also, potentially, between dental tissues and residual restorative materials, which differ in absorption, scattering, and water content [5], [9], [14].

In secondary caries management, a DRS probe could provide objective, operator-independent, real-time feedback, reducing the risk of residual composite retention—an issue not reliably addressed by current diagnostic methods, as highlighted by recent meta-analytical evidence. In endodontic retreatment, DRS may improve localization of gutta-percha and sealer remnants, thereby minimizing unnecessary removal of radicular dentin and reducing the risk of structural weakening. Integration with machine learning algorithms, which have achieved classification accuracies exceeding 98%, further enhances the diagnostic capability of the method [2], [6], [13], [23].

Clinical translation requires *in vivo* validation under intraoral conditions, optimization of probe design for endodontic access, and development of a comprehensive spectral reference database for commonly used dental materials. Nevertheless, current evidence suggests that DRS represents a meaningful advancement in the dental diagnostic armamentarium, supporting precise, objective, and non-destructive identification of tissues and materials in minimally invasive dentistry.

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